

STUDENTS' COMPETENCIES IN FIELD STUDY (FS) COURSES OF TEACHERS EDUCATION INSTITUTIONS (TEIs) IN BATANGAS PROVINCE

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ABSTRACT

This study described the field study students in terms of attitudes and behaviour, study habits and communication skills. Extent of students' competencies in experiential learning courses was also determined by FS students, supervisors and cooperating teachers. This also covered the issues and concerns in FS courses with the end view of preparing differentiated experiential learning activities to help the students develop their competencies. The descriptive method of research was utilized in the study with the use of questionnaire, and supplemented by informal interviews and focus group discussion. Respondents were FS supervisors, cooperating teachers and field study students from selected TEIs and selected elementary and secondary schools in the province of Batangas. The study used were weighted mean, F-test or ANOVA, Pearson -r and Scheffe test. The results revealed that FS students possessed and described the desired attitudes and behaviour, study habits and communication skills which are necessary in FS courses and manifested competencies in exploring the curriculum. There were significant relationships between the FS students' description and their extent of manifestation in FS courses and significant differences on assessments of the three respondent groups of FS students' competencies. Insufficient orientation program intended for FS students and limited time of cooperating teachers to attend to FS students' needs were identified and prepared to enhance the competencies of FS students. It was recommended the prepared differentiated learning activities be endorsed to the TEIs for further review, suggestions and later be prepared for utilization. Frequent orientation programs for FS students may be conducted by TEI's in partnership with cooperating schools for better implementation of FS courses and conduct similar study to validate the results where likewise recommended.

Keywords: teacher education, competencies, descriptive method